

EDUCATION TRANSFER KNOWLEDGE 10.

Training Platform for SPOC Delivery

Project Information

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In the present document, the key functionalities of the Learning Management System (LMS) for training of University Tutors (Lectures), School Tutors (school teachers, cooperating teachers, mentors) and Student Teachers (Prospective Teachers) are outlined (further, SPOC or Course). These are added with the key features of the main EKT App (see WP4) that are going to be used for the training, and are aligned with the Methodological Framework (WP3). In essence, the approach in Output 10 can be described as integrating the expertise and capacities of the EKT partners to develop solutions that

- 1. Most contribute to the purpose of the EKT Project.**
- 2. That are aligned with the Methodological Framework developed in WP3**
- 3. Create a user-friendly learning environment**

Importantly, both the LMS for the courses and the main EKT App have become to constitute a separate but connected architecture of the planned online course.

2. KEY FUNCTIONALITIES OF THE LMS

The LMS for the Training is Chamilo: a free software e-learning and content management system; added with an innovative content creation tool, the Netex ContentCloud.

The choice for the system lies in the following rationale:

- 1. We aim to integrate the capacities of the EKT partners:** Beeznest, an official Chamilo provider, and Netex, that develops apps and services for e-learning.
- 2. The affordances that the LMS provides.** Further, the key functionalities and an overview of the LMS are described; as adapted for the SPOC purposes.

Chamilo: is the platform where the SPOC takes place, and it can be accessed from the Training Tool on the EKT Platform. Within the course, the following tools are available ([Picture 1](#)):

- **Course header:** EKT logo and course name
- **Course description:** The place where to describe the objectives of the course, outcomes, methodology, resources, assessment, etc.
- **Learning path:** it is the place where the training actions take place through the addition of structured content as a timeline. The elements of the timeline can be visible letting the user choose the opening order or on the other side can be blocked and make mandatory the view of an element prior to the following one. A learning path can contain multiple elements: content, files, tests, links, and assignments. Part of the Content is integrated from the NETEX Contentcloud. The most valuable feature of Chamilo is that the learning paths can be assigned to different students. It is also possible to view the results/progress of the students and give them feedback. The SPOC has one learning path however its activities are targeted at student teachers, school mentors and academic mentors.
- **Activities:** these are the SPOC units that are integrated then into the Learning Path. The activities include contents such as tutorial videos, descriptions etc., and tasks for student teachers, academic mentors and student teachers.
- **Portfolio:** This is one of the key tools for the Course since there is a goal to engage student teachers in reflective practice and academic tutors and school mentors in supporting students with their expertise. This tool was created by the partners specifically for the EKT Project with the methodological framework in mind. There is a general portfolio for the course in which all the students and all the tutors/mentors of the course can publish posts and comments but also every student has his own portfolio in which he/she is the only one who can publish posts and the tutors and other students can access only to add comments instead of new entries. Each post is composed of a title, a content block (text, files, images, etc.) and tags to mark/categorize it. If a student considers a post on the public portfolio as valuable, it can be added to their own portfolio in order to work/reflect with/on it. The tutor can also send some post to other student own portfolio. Marks can be added at portfolio, post or comment levels. In the Course, we aim to engage the 'students' with all the features of the tool, and demonstrate how the tool can be used for the in-school placement purposes. The ePortfolio has its unique structure based on the WP3 methodology.

The **e-portfolio has been structured in 3 sections:** Reflections, Materials, Final Report, according to the type of content included in each of the 6 stages of the EKT methodology (see Output 6).

In sum, Portfolio is a very important element of the SPOC and the platform, and it is planned that the tool is used throughout the SPOC and the entire Pilot (at all phases described in WP3) to support reflective practice and follow-up of students.

- **Content Creation Tool** : The SPOC students will have an access and need to try to create educational contents with the content creation tool called Chamilo Studio. This tool allows student teachers to create different multimedia contents. The contents are in SCORM format, this means that they can be exported.

Picture 1: Screenshot of Chamilo Tools used for the SPOC Piloted

3. KEY FUNCTIONALITIES OF THE EKT PLATFORM

Although the SPOC happens in the LMS Chamilo, it aims to engage the three groups (university tutor, school tutor and student teachers) with the EKT Platform tools ([Picture 2](#)). This means that the key activities (beyond the Portfolio tool) for the three groups are planned in the Main EKT Platform space developed by the EKT Partners, technical board. The key functionalities of the EKT Platform are outlined further. They are grouped in the key sections of the EKT Platform.

Management: is a key tool for administrative purposes. It assembles the required information about the users, assigns the tutors, school tutors and student teachers to each other, create a group of users based on a year / course. It also allows creating courses for some roles: it is possible to create new courses to the platform, list the created courses, list the enrolled courses, etc. It can be used for the administrative tasks: (depending on the role) a direct access to the “deck” or “tasks” tool. For Pilot and the SPOC, EKT partners are going to create the users for each partner university using this Tool. In the SPOC, we provide a video on how to create users, manage them by assigning student teachers to university tutors and school tutors. In addition, we ask all course participants to check their profiles and complete the missing information (avatar, address, telephone etc.).

Document Cloud: Includes all the tools related with file/folder management, chat-video communication and calendar, and is an important element for the SPOC. The communication and exchange of documents during the SPOC happens in this section. It is accessible from the main desktop dashboard through the following accesses:

- **My files:** Possibility to create private files and folders (2GB) per user. Shared folders between users on demand. Automated group shared folders depending on the role. Possibility to edit files (word, excel, etc.) online and collaboratively. On the SPOC, we engage the course participants in tasks that require the use of this Tool and that are connected to the methodological Framework (WP3).
- **Communication:** Possibility to communicate with one or several users via chat or videoconference. The chat supports both synchronous and asynchronous communication. Possibility to create conversation groups. Automated groups depending on the role. The communication tool is multidevice capable through an app (iOS and Android). Possibility to share/embed documents from “my files” within the conversation. The same with links and external documents. “Raise hand” within a videocall. On the SPOC, we use the Communication Tool as (1) forum for the SPOC by creating conversation groups where a challenge question can be discussed; (2) as a means of private messaging between the three target groups to make certain arrangements; (3) as a videoconference tool for the SPOC short webinars, and for the university tutors, school tutors and student teachers to work on their SPOC tasks collaboratively and discuss certain issues.
- **Calendar:** The element can encompass a number of calendars where each user can add/edit/remove their own appointments. Possibility to share appointments with concrete users or with groups (depending on the role). Videoconference rooms can be linked to calendar events. Possibility to add reminders and to set repetition on certain appointments. On the SPOC, we use the Calendar Tool as
 1. The SPOC calendar shared with all the course participants with important events and deadlines.
 2. A task for the course participants to use the tool for their in-school placement purposes, to make the necessary arrangements etc.

Chamilo Studio: Content Creation Tool. In Unit 4, we engage student teachers in creating e-materials using the Chamilo Studio Tool, and share their products with academic mentors and other student teachers.

Help section: This is the part of the platform where the users can find useful information about both the technical use of the platform and the methodology of the EKT system. The section contains tutorials, documentation, videos, and a FAQ section and contact forms in case of errors with the platform. This Section will be active during the SPOC. First, the participants will be able to find the tutorials around the EKT system developed together by the EKT Partners Lusoinfo, Cesga and the University College of Teacher Education Vienna; the manual developed by Cesga, and the ongoing technical support in the FAQ section.

Picture 2: The EKT Platform Tools (second pilot version)

4. CONCLUSION

To conclude: in the development of the training for university tutors, school tutors and student teachers we aimed to engage the participants with all the tools that the EKT system affords: Management, Document Cloud, Communication Tool, Calendar Tool, Chamilo Studio; in a variety of ways to demonstrate possibilities for their use. Although the SPOC is placed in the Chamilo LMS, it actually happens and develops in the entire EKT system (including the EKT Platform and EKT App for communication).

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